

“A lot of the presses I like are scholar-led, embedded within their academic disciplines. You have this quality to it, because it’s being not just submitted by an expert, it’s being shaped by an expert in the field, edited by one and sometimes even copy edited by one.”

Dr Samuel Moore, a scholarly communications specialist at Cambridge University Library, is an early career researcher publishing his first monograph open access through a community press.

Open access facilitates community-led publishing, which Moore thinks is a very positive development. It encourages experimentation with form, content and audience participation, while adhering to the same high standards as traditional publishing.

Moore explains: “Publishing open access felt to me like a traditional publishing experience in terms of copy editing, peer reviews and such like.”

Moore’s advice for finding a credible open access book publisher

Tap into the rise of community, scholar-led presses

Pick a professional press with high publishing standards

Check the quality of the process, that peer review, copy editing and the editorial board all adhere to high standards

Look around because there are options